

TEACHING THROUGH THE THEATRE: A SPLASH INTO LOCAL THEATRE AND ITS
IMPACT ON THE COMMUNITY

by

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The Two Roles

Theatre, as a collaborative art form, depends on cooperation between departments. I served a dual purpose during my Senior Honors Project. For Stagelight Family Production's *The Little Mermaid*, I took on the roles of director and stage manager. When I pitched this project, my producer questioned my sanity, but I was determined to prove that the same person could take on both tasks.

The director must act as the funnel through which ideas flow: actors, choreographers, and musical directors all put forth ideas, and the director then must ensure that the ideas selected create a cohesive vision and coherently convey the story.

The stage manager is responsible for acting as the liaison between technical and creative aspects of the production, eventually calls all technical aspects of the show, ensures the safety of all parties throughout the rehearsal and performance process, and maintains the director's vision once they have left. In this case, because I was both stage manager and director, the final task shall be the most fluid combination.

Both are crucial roles on which the entire process of Western theatre relies. Many pieces integrated easily, while others took adapting, planning, and relied on the overall production team's cooperation to enact effectively. The key to a successful production is effective collaboration, led by the director and facilitated by the stage manager.

History

I began my journey in the theatrical arts through Stagelight Family Productions in 2008. It only fits that my directorial debut should be one of their well-orchestrated productions, *The Little Mermaid*, in their 2023 Winter season.

As this production's director and stage manager, I orchestrated two casts of approximately 250, each with 27 lead characters. As the director, I lead character work, staged the show, and worked collaboratively with a team of creatives (choreographers, musical directors, and designers) to adhere to a cohesive vision. Simultaneously, as the stage manager, I worked to actualize the creatives' ideas through production calendars, tracking documents, and, eventually, calling all technical aspects of the production during the show.

I chose to dedicate my project to community theatre, specifically youth theatre; I believe theatre teaches young people essential life skills: empathy, self-confidence, public speaking, team building, leadership, and so many more.

I further developed my directorial toolbox, as I had the opportunity to work with a cast that included actors from five-years old through adult, with a vast expanse of theatrical experience, ranging from nonexistent to professional. The expansive cast required me to utilize different tactics of communication to produce the desired results. I am grateful to have the chance to shape young minds in the same program that was so influential in shaping my own.

Pre-Production

Before either directing or stage managing a production, I first needed to gather various types of data. In terms of directing, this included in depth textual analysis, which I could later use to formulate any concepts for the production. In terms of stage managing this meant, "prep week," a time during which the stage manager connects with the production team, designers, producer, and directors. During this time, the stage manager also sets up documents and templates for future paperwork so that the show runs smoothly.

Textual Analysis

Following guidelines from my advanced directing courses, I began my textual analysis with an analysis of plot, further breaking down Aristotelian plot elements into: Inciting Incident (an event that occurs before the play, which is the reason the play begins there it does), Departure Point (the situation when the play begins), Galvanizing Event (the event that focuses the story), Crisis (an event that ratchets up the tension and puts protagonist and antagonist in a metaphorical or literal battle to the death), Climax (the highest point of tension), and Denouement (the falling action). For this play, the inciting incident is when Ariel sneaks to the surface again, before "World Above," the departure point is when she sings about wanting to be in the world above, the galvanizing event is when Ursula plots to take down Triton by using Ariel as bait, the crisis is when Ursula steals Ariel from the surface during the contest, and the climax is when Ariel kills Ursula by breaking her shell. Therefore, the denouement is everything after this point, including when Ariel and Triton apologize to one another, when she re-transforms into a human, when Eric proposes, and when Ariel and Eric get married. Once these

basic elements of plot were determined, I continued to isolate the major complications that lead up to the crisis of the play, which helped focus the climax of each scene and relate it to the overall story.

After an analysis of plot, I moved on to an analysis of character. Ariel, also known as the Little Mermaid, is the protagonist of the play, described as a fiery redhead and clever. She is the youngest daughter of King Triton and is accused of getting special treatment due to her age and her voice, as special as her late mother's was. More than anything, Ariel needs to belong. She explores the surface, misses the concert, saves Eric, mourns the loss of her grotto, makes a deal with her aunt, the sea witch, has dinner and dances Eric, follows Eric to his special place, dances at the singing contest to fight for her relationship with the prince, kills Ursula to protect her father, then finally she accepts Eric's proposal and marries him, all to belong to and join his world. When casting her, it is important to consider her required vocal ability (mezzo-soprano) and dance ability (tap would be preferable).

Eric, an ally in the play, and the love interest, is a prince of a coastal human kingdom. He is described as handsome and adventurous. He is a tenor-baritone with moderate dance ability. He mourns the recent loss of his father and resents the idea that he should take over the kingdom when he would much rather explore the sea with his fellow sailors. A near death experience leads him to search for his savior, but along the way he finds Ariel lost on the shore and pledges to help her. Through his relationship with Ariel, he learns the importance of genuine connection and grows to accept his responsibility as king, acknowledging that there should be a balance between passion and responsibility.

Grimsby makes a transition from antagonist to ally. Described as Eric's "droll British guardian," Grimsby attempts to find Eric a wife, as was the king's dying wish. Grimsby pressures Eric to wed a princess and better the kingdom's prospects, but, through witnessing Eric's love for Ariel, comes to appreciate the strength and stability her love will bring the kingdom (though his traditional ways are satisfied when he realizes she too is royalty).

Ariel receives help from her three friends: a fish named Flounder who is hopelessly in love with her, a seagull named Scuttle who is a self-declared expert on "human stuff" and benevolently misguides her on the intricacies human life, and finally a crab named Sebastian, who is a talented musician, tasked by Triton with keeping an eye on the youngest princess. Sebastian decides to go against Triton's wishes, trading obedience to the king for an attempt at bringing Ariel true happiness. Though Sebastian is usually a stickler for the rules, when Ariel is in trouble, he is always there.

King Triton has a similar arc to Grimsby. He is the king of the sea and a widower. For the past 15 years, Triton has blamed human beings for murdering his wife and leaving him as the single father of seven daughters. However, the true murderer was his sister Ursula, whom he banished many years ago. Because of his belief, he insists his daughters stay away from humans and deems their entire species dangerous. It takes Ariel proving the humans' innocence for him to approve her marriage to a human prince.

The sea witch Ursula is Triton's half-sister. She is Poseidon's illegitimate daughter, who was discriminated against for being a squid. To take revenge on her father and her family for their ignorance, she killed her six older sisters and father, temporarily overtaking the throne. However, when her baby brother, Triton, came of age, the kingdom preferred the male heir over

the tyrannical ruler and Triton banished her for her crimes against the kingdom. To seek revenge on Triton, Ursula convinces Ariel to sell her voice and soul in exchange for time on land, using Triton's daughter as bait to lure him into giving up his kingdom. She is an alto with a strong belt.

Ariel has six older sisters: Aquata, the vicious leader, Adella, the wall flower, Allana, the sweet one, Arista, the beauty queen, Atina, the middle child, and Andrina, the brains. In order from eldest to youngest, the sisters go: Aquata, Andrina, Arista, Atina, Adella, Allana, and Ariel. Though the sisters are jealous of Ariel, they come to support her in the end. These girls must have strong vocal ability and decent dance ability. In act two, the same actresses will play the six princesses in the contest for Eric's hand.

Other notable characters include: Windward and Leeward: servants to King Triton who, as trumpetfish, announce his entrances (Their names mean facing toward and away from the wind, respectively, as in sailing). Flotsam and Jetsam: Two eels who serve Ursula. (Their names mean junk lost at sea.). The Pilot is Eric's right hand man when aboard their ship, and leads a crew of sailors. Chef Louis, a French master chef, serves in Eric's castle and specializes in seafood dishes. Chef Louis controls a regime of chefs who also work in the castle. Other castle staff include the maids, who report to Grimsby and show jealousy towards Ariel's blossoming relationship with Eric.

The ensemble in this production will play fish when below the sea, then turtles, frogs, and birds when in the lagoons. Dancers will represent water personified and tapping seagulls when on the beach.

After analyzing character, I moved onto language. Analysis of language included a close read of each song as well as determining the purpose of each song. The opening song, "World Above," is Ariel's first I Want song, where she begins by establishing her desire to join the beautiful human world. "Fathoms Below" establishes Prince Eric's desire to live at sea and forgo his responsibilities as a king. "The Daughters of Triton" introduces Triton, Sebastian, Ariel's sisters, and the idea that Ariel is escaping her responsibilities by gawking at the human world. "If Only (Triton's Lament)" portrays Triton's desire to do what is right for his daughters and describes how he mourns his wife and is lost without her. "Daddy's Little Angel" contextualizes Ursula's resentment for the merpeople and Triton. The song depicts her plot to destroy the king through Ariel. "Part of Your World" further develops Ariel's desire to join the human world and the reprise of this song focuses this desire on her love for Prince Eric and how she wants to be alongside him. "She's in Love" shows the sister's realization that their youngest sister has been overtaken by love and serves largely as a spectacle piece. In "Her Voice," Prince Eric yearns to find the woman who saved his life and made him feel whole. "Under the Sea" is an attempt by Sebastian and all the sea creatures to convince Ariel how fortunate she is to have the home she has. "If Only (Ariel's Lament)" distances Ariel from her father and insists she hates his oppression. "Sweet Child" is a promise by Flotsam and Jetsam that Ursula has the answer to all of Ariel's problems, which leads into Ursula's proposition "Poor Unfortunate Souls," which she uses to convince Ariel that she is on the princesses' side. Act two opens with another spectacle piece, "Positoovity," during which the seagulls teach Ariel to use her human legs. In "Beyond My Wildest Dreams" Ariel reaffirms that she wants Eric and is happy with her life on the shore. Eric attempts to bridge a communication barrier and deepen his connection with Ariel in "One Step Closer." In "Kiss the Girl," Eric and Ariel grow closer, through the help of Ariel's friends

pushing them together. "If Only," the quartet, serves as an I Want song for Ariel, Eric, Triton, and Sebastian. Ariel wants to be loved, Eric wants to let go of Her Voice so he can focus on the girl before him, Triton wants his daughter back safely, and Sebastian would give up the world to see his best friend happy. "The Contest" is a comedic piece which shows the princesses competing with Ariel for Eric. Ursula puts the last of her plan into action in the reprise of "Poor Unfortunate Souls," when she pulls Ariel back under the sea and makes a deal with Triton to sell his soul in exchange for his daughter's, but Ariel outwits her by breaking her magic shell. Finally, both kingdoms combine to celebrate the love between Ariel and Eric in "Finale Ultimo."

As it is a musical about a woman who transforms from mermaid to human princess, the show is filled with spectacle and music. Composed by Alan Menken, there are harmonies and musical dynamics, which are used to aid in the story telling. Additionally, the play offers the challenge of visually representing fish and other animals, a shipwreck, several transformations, and multiple locations (on the beach, various parts of the sea, and in several rooms of the castle).

Final preparation before I could begin my conceptual design included a catalog of all "facts" of the play, or any rules and circumstances provided by the playwright (for example: Ursula derives all her power from the magic shell that was gifted to her by her father Poseidon).

Concept

The themes that I find significant to this play are love, family, revenge, duty, and freedom. Both Ariel and Eric have important relationships to paternal figures in their lives, and I use staging to create parallels between Ariel and Triton and Eric and Grimsby.

In addition to the use of sliders, which will create a distinct backdrop for when we are inside of the castle, I played with movement to create the idea that their environments affected them differently. If a character was from the land, they were bouncier and had sharper movements. An underwater character had more fluid movement and all lead fish (Triton, mersisters, Flounder, Flotsam, and Jetsam) were on a version of a roller-skate, which allowed them to glide across the stage.

Finally, to further create the idea that we were underwater, I wanted to make all the transitions flow from one place to the next. For example, if we were moving underwater, the water dancers would take us there and, in the castle, maids and chefs moved scenery to emphasize that they worked in the castle.

Prep Week

As the stage manager, my prep week included a tech analysis (an in-depth analysis of all technical aspects suggested in the script. For example, when a light shift, sound, or effect is suggested) I also compiled props and costumes lists, collected rehearsal props, formulated a rehearsal schedule, made a quick change plot in accordance with the company's past production, formatted my blocking script with a ground plan diagram, built templates for shift plots and other necessary paperwork, and created a dictionary for all words in the script that may be unfamiliar to actors (ex. Fathoms: (plural noun) a unit of length equal to six feet, chiefly used to indicate the depth of water).

Casting Process

As a stage manager, I assisted in the casting process by creating organizational documents, such as audition and call backs schedules, callback guides which corresponded to the sides each character had to prepare, and finally building the cast list. I set up the room and ran auditions by calling names and keeping to a time schedule. Additionally, I sent out callback emails to each of the 109 individuals that had to be called back.

As a director, my first duty with the cast is to create it. We held auditions in three stages. First, there was a pre-audition. During this time, the choreographer and musical director taught an age-appropriate audition cut for all participants to perform at auditions. Because this is community theatre and there is a vast range of experience among those auditioning, we found it easiest to provide the group with pre-cut audition pieces from the show. The eldest age group, from which we pulled most of the leads, had three choices for songs, that way they could choose the one that best fit their voice and the character they were auditioning for. This also helped during the callback process. Day two were the auditions. Performers danced in groups of five. Groups A and B then sang in the same groups of five. Group C sang individually. After auditions were completed, the production team met briefly to discuss who would be called back for what role. The final day was filled with callbacks, beginning with the youngest roles, moving on to principal roles, and finishing the day with secondary characters. We met after callbacks and discussed the cast list, but decided we were missing men from the group announced an open virtual audition for the role of Eric. After viewing video submissions, the production team reconvened to finalize the cast list and release it to the public.

Casting inevitably breaks hearts and encourages politics to enter the conversation. One of the most important lessons I learned as a young director, through this casting process and reflecting on the final product, is that my gut is often correct in casting. While I understand that casting is, by nature, a political process, I allowed the casting of this show to become far too political. Because I was so grateful for the opportunity, I was afraid to push back against my producer's strong personality and fight for the casting decisions I preferred. In the end, I decided to concede on several roles, and was met two weeks into the rehearsal process with the producer questioning, "Why did we cast *them*?" I wish that I had stood my ground because even if I was met with the same questioning for my choices, at least I would not have sacrificed my integrity.

Rehearsal

Running the Rehearsal Room

As I entered the rehearsal room, the roles of stage manager and director grew more fluid and interchangeable. By nature, I am a very organized director. I work best on a schedule and crossing off specific goals, which corresponds very well with the duty of a stage manager in the rehearsal room: to keep the team on track while thinking of the bigger picture and how all technical and creative elements will collide. Additionally, it is traditional for the stage manager to take blocking notation based on the director's staging. Because I was the director, I already had this notation and only needed to update my notes on the rare occasion of a change.

Rehearsals were divided into ensemble and lead rehearsals. In ensemble rehearsals, because the cast was so large, my main function was in running tracks, keeping tabs on where each member of the cast was to be placed, and helping to manage the room.

Lead rehearsals began with a table read, separated by cast. Each cast read through the entire script and opened a dialogue about the story as a whole and each scene/song. I utilized a tactic I had seen done by my mentor, Mark Ramont, where during the table read each song was spoken through as if an extension of the text. I believe this strategy is especially effective in young musical theatre actors, as it emphasizes the idea that dialogue and song are a continuous being and that song lyrics deserve just as much motivation and analysis as any line of dialogue.

After the table read, lead rehearsals were subdivided into three sections: dance, vocal, and staging. As the director, I was responsible for staging all dialogue and some of the ballads which did not require dance ability. I collaborated with my musical director and choreographers to ensure that the dance and songs flowed well with the scenes between them and that they served to continue and deepen the story telling.

Along with staging, I scheduled character work with each lead character. This was transformational, especially because many of the young actors had never done any kind of table work or character analysis before. This analysis helped them to deepen their understanding of relationship and activate the action in their scenes.

Once we moved into the theatre, I switched more heavily into my stage manager mode, as I needed to finalize all technical aspects of the show. However, as a director, I still needed to collaborate with designers and advocate for my vision. I was very lucky to have a skilled team that was on my side and who understood exactly what I needed.

Performance

Calling the Show

The final aspect of stage managing a production is calling the show. Over the course of tech week, I built a calling script, which included all the cues that I needed to tell various departments to enact to keep the show running smoothly. These departments included lights, sound (both tracks and microphones), deck/scenic, haze, spotlights, and rigging.

My primary goal during the production was to ensure safety of all parties and my secondary goal was to keep the show running smoothly. Both directors and stage managers are problem solvers. Several times during the show run, I had to think on my feet and calmly instruct others to orchestrate solutions to maintain the show's vision in the face of mishaps. For example, opening night, our light board crashed and none of the cues in act two were correct. Luckily, I knew the show well enough, and my board operator was savvy enough, so I was able to use the Magic Sheet (a one sheet, which depicts where every light in the space is pointing) to design the show as we went along. It was not the beautiful design we had during tech week, but it enabled the audience to see all the key moments in the show. The designer then returned that night and restored the show file.

Audience and Cast Reaction

Both the audience and cast were overwhelmingly supportive of this production. Several accounts arose of parents praising our producer for bringing me in, mentioning that I was truly influential in their child's growth as a performer.

In an anonymous survey I conducted of the leads of both casts, 90% of those who responded ranked their performance and the overall production a nine or higher out of 10.

When asked to reflect on my job as a director, the following responses were recorded.

What was the best part about working with Kylie as a director?

21 responses

Her energy and positive feedback

She was so nice and accepted all of our ideas

She was clear and gave constructive criticism, instead of just telling me I did a good job.

Very open to my input as an actor. VERY collaborative.

I loved the things we learned and the new experiences we had and also I liked her kindness and how open she was

She was supportive of each person

Getting to work with someone who was new and had different ideas

her being understanding and character work

The constant motivation and support to help push us to be better performers.

What was the best part about working with Kylie as a director?

21 responses

The constant motivation and support to help push us to be better performers.

Getting real actual direction for the first time. It felt good to know what and why I was doing something on stage.

Kylie is such a sweet director and treats everyone like a friend not a coworker which makes the environment so much more enjoyable. stan kylie

She's very funny and easy to talk her and i felt i really grew as an actor

she's super cool and i used to be afraid of her but now i'm not cuz she's nice :)

Her flexibility and understanding

excellent at collaborating with actors, and making innovative performance choices

super fun to work with and i really enjoyed the character work

She's so fun to work with! She's one of the homies.

She is really understanding, and she always finds a way to make me smile when I'm feeling out of it.

everything was very organized and time efficient

She encouraged me and made sure to thank me whenever I had to fill in for a show or come to a rehearsal on short notice.

Definitely the specificity in the vision and rehearsal process. The blocks of time we were called for was accurate and I felt consistent.

What is something Kylie could improve upon as a director?

17 responses

More rehearsals for parts that are not singing and dancing although I do understand with this type of production the musical numbers are most important

Nothing

Not much, maybe just more communication to actors.

Spend time or assign someone to work more with the minor characters. Leads and ensemble were well rehearsed

Nothing. She is the best!

Relax and have fun

Can't think of anything

Being more stern

What is something Kylie could improve upon as a director?

17 responses

When giving notes, be more specific and stern. If you want something to change make it more clear.

NOTHING, she slays every day.

idk

Maybe giving more complimentary notes

more specificity with notes, even then though- you were specific.

Maybe clearer notes.

I can't think of anything.

maybe halfway through rehearsals ask performers what they need more work on

Probably maybe being a little more specific with notes

The most significant takeaway from this survey was that it was an overall positive experience for all cast members who responded, many felt I helped them grow as performers, and moving forward, I could work on being more demanding of my actors and clarifying the language I use to give notes.

I have more experience as a stage manager, and the cast responded to the same questions about my stage management skills with an overwhelming "nothing to be improved upon" and repeated compliments on my organization and communication skills. Granted, I am positive that I have things to improve upon, but from a young actor's perspective, it is good to know I am doing well.

Conclusion

Because of this project, I have a deepened love for stage management and directing. Communication and organization are crucial to both roles, as are leadership skills and a strong sense of self. A stage manager must facilitate communication between all directorial aspects of the production. This process took out the middleman.

The double duty hurt me in only one notable circumstance: I edited my directorial concepts before they came to fruition because of technical concerns, whereas one would typically present the idea and then edit it. I think that, at times, this stifled creativity. Since I have been hired this summer for both roles through the same company for a production of *Mary Poppins*, I will learn from this mistake and be more deliberate about separating the processes of creating and editing. "Try everything," as Mark Ramont says.

I attribute much of my success in this production to my incredible team of collaborators, who inspired me daily and were always willing to take risks and play. Our technical director often says: "but it could be better," and this mantra pushed us out of complacency. We tried not to settle for a choice we knew could improve.

Though I proved it was possible to combine these two roles, splitting them allows everyone to be more present in their job. Especially on a more professional show, I think it would be in everyone's best interest to hire two dedicated people for these positions.

Nevertheless, the key to success is collaboration. I could successfully mount this production, even taking on two significant roles, because I surrounded myself with an excellent team. Their passion and talent made the production a success.